

Article

Is There a Woman in *Los Candidatos*? Gender Perception with Masculine “Generics” and Gender-Fair Language Strategies in Spanish

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Abstract

This study examines how several gender-encoding strategies in Spanish and social factors influence gender perception, reinforcing or mitigating a sexist male bias. Using an experimental design, we tested four linguistic conditions in a job recruitment context: masculine forms (theoretically generic), gender-splits, epicenes, and non-binary neomorpheme “-e”. After reading a profile in one of these conditions, 837 participants (52% women) selected an image of a woman or man. Results show that masculine forms lead to the lowest selection of female candidates, manifesting a male bias. In contrast, gender-fair language (GFL) strategies, particularly the neomorpheme (*les candidatas*), elicited the highest selection of female images. Importantly, not only did linguistic factors and participants’ gender identity influence results—with male participants selecting significantly more men in the masculine condition, but affinity with feminist movements and LGBTQIA+ communities or positive attitudes towards GFL also modulated responses—increasing female selections in GFL, but reinforcing male selections in the masculine. Additionally, no extra cognitive cost was found for GFL strategies compared to masculine expressions. These findings highlight the importance, not only of linguistic forms, but of social and attitudinal factors in shaping gender perception, with implications for reducing gender biases in language use and broader efforts toward social equity.

Keywords: male bias; gender-fair language; masculine generics; Spanish; non-binary neomorphemes; gender splits; sexism; feminism; attitudes

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1. Introduction

A *male bias* in language perception refers to the tendency to interpret expressions that are ambiguous, or which do not include grammatical gender cues (i.e., morphological information on the gender of the referent), as referring to men only (cf. Stahlberg et al., 2007). Experimental research on gender biases over the last decades has shown this male bias to be a persistent phenomenon across languages with or without grammatical gender distinctions¹ (Hamilton, 1991; Stahlberg et al., 2007; Garnham et al., 2012, among others).

In this light, and particularly in grammatical gender languages, the traditional use of masculine forms with an intended *generic* interpretation (that is, to refer to mix-gender